

Statistical Analysis Plan

TRIAL FULL TITLE	PRedicting Outcomes For Crohn's disease using a moLecular biomarkEr (PROFILE) trial
EUDRACT NUMBER	
SAP VERSION	
ISRCTN NUMBER	ISRCTN11808228
SAP VERSION DATE	
TRIAL STATISTICIAN	Simon Bond
TRIAL CHIEF INVESTIGATOR	Miles Parkes
SAP AUTHOR	Simon Bond

1 SAP Signatures

I give my approval for the attached SAP entitled Profile Final Analysis dated Version 1.0 23 February 2023

Chief Investigator

Name: Miles Parkes

Signature:

Date: 6th Feb 2023

Statistician

Name: Simon Bond

Signature:

Date: 6 Feb 2023